

Nexus Between Information Technology and Telecommunications: Academic Libraries'

Bilgi Teknolojisi ve Telekomünikasyon Arasındaki Bağlantı: Akademik Kütüphanelerin Yönü

Olayinka MAKİNDE^{1,*}
Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

Temitope OLATUNJI²
Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

Andrew Olukunmi
IGBINLOLA³
Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

Sarah vou GYANG⁴
National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja,
Nigeria

Geliş Tarihi/Received 24.05.2024
Kabul Tarihi/Accepted 20.06.2024
Yayın Tarihi/Publication Date 30.06.2024

Sorumlu Yazar/Corresponding author:
Olayinka MAKİNDE
E-mail:
makinde.olayinka@adelekeuniversity.edu.
ng

Cite this article: Makinde, O., Olatunji, T., Igbinalola, A. O., & vou Gyang, S. (2024). Nexus between information technology and telecommunications: Academic libraries'. *Education and Technology in Information Science*, 2(1), 25-35.

Content of this journal is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of Information Technology (IT) and telecommunications has transformed various aspects of modern society, including academic libraries. This research explores the nexus between IT, telecommunications and academic libraries and how their integration can foster an inclusive and equitable research environment within universities. It examines the historical development of IT and telecommunications, the evolving role of academic libraries in the digital era, and the challenges and opportunities posed by digital transformation. The study highlights the integration of IT and telecommunications in academic library services, such as digital collections, virtual reference and collaborative platforms, enabling remote access, interdisciplinary research and knowledge sharing. Strategies for enhancing research inclusion, such as investing in technological infrastructure, promoting open access initiatives and providing digital literacy training are discussed. Successful implementation examples from Nigerian academic libraries are presented, demonstrating the practical application of these technologies. Additionally, the research examines emerging trends and technologies and proposes strategies for academic libraries to adapt and remain relevant in the evolving landscape. The conclusion emphasizes the importance of collaboration among policymakers, researchers and library professionals to leverage the transformative potential of IT and telecommunications for research inclusion and societal progress.

Keywords: Information technology, telecommunications, academic libraries, digital transformation, research inclusion

Öz

Bilgi Teknolojisi (BT) ve telekomünikasyondaki hızlı ilerleme, akademik kütüphaneler de dahil olmak üzere modern toplumun çeşitli yönlerini dönüştürdü. Bu çalışmada BT, telekomünikasyon ve akademik kütüphaneler arasındaki bağı ve bunların entegrasyonunun üniversitelerde kapsayıcı ve eşitlikçi bir araştırma ortamını nasıl teşvik edebileceği araştırılmıştır. BT ve telekomünikasyonun tarihsel gelişimi, dijital çağda akademik kütüphanelerin değişen rolü ve dijital dönüşümün getirdiği zorluklar ve fırsatlar literatür bağlamında incelenmiştir. Çalışma, dijital koleksiyonlar, sanal referans ve işbirlikçi platformlar gibi akademik kütüphane hizmetlerinde BT ve telekomünikasyonun uzaktan erişim, disiplinler arası araştırma ve bilgi paylaşımına olanak sağlayan entegrasyonunu vurgulamaktadır. Teknolojik altyapıya yatırım yapmak, açık erişim girişimlerini teşvik etmek ve dijital okuryazarlık eğitimi sağlamak gibi araştırmaya katılımı artırmaya yönelik stratejiler tartışılmaktadır. Nijerya akademik kütüphanelerinden başarılı uygulama örnekleri sunularak bu teknolojilerin pratik uygulamaları gösterilmiştir. Ayrıca çalışmada, ortaya çıkan trendler ve teknolojiler incelenmiş ve akademik kütüphanelerin gelişen ortama uyum sağlamaları ve bu ortama uygun kalmaları için stratejiler önerilmiştir. Sonuçta, araştırma katılımı ve toplumsal ilerleme için BT ve telekomünikasyonun dönüştürücü potansiyelinden yararlanmak amacıyla politika yapımcılar, araştırmacılar ve kütüphane uzmanları arasındaki iş birliğinin önemi vurgulanmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bilgi teknolojisi, telekomünikasyon, akademik kütüphaneler, dijital dönüşüm, araştırmaya katılım

Introduction

The rapid advancement in Information Technology (IT) and telecommunications has changed nearly every aspect of modern society, transforming the way we live, work and communicate. Information Technology encompasses the use of computers, software and networks to store, process and transmit data and information (Singh, 2021). Telecommunications, on the other hand, refers to the transmission of information over long distances using various technologies, such as telephone lines, radio waves and fiber optic cables (Umoren & Agwunobi, 2017). The convergence of IT and telecommunications has paved the way for innovations, such as the Internet, mobile devices and cloud computing, which have profoundly impacted global connectivity, information sharing and access to resources.

The Internet, in particular, has emerged as a powerful platform for communication, e-commerce and online collaboration enabling individuals and organizations to transcend geographical boundaries (Galiullina & Wright, 2021). Mobile devices, like smartphones and tablets, have further enhanced the connectivity of technology-driven gadgets, allowing users to access information and communicate virtually anywhere (Demir & Akpinar, 2018). Moreover, these technologies have played a crucial role in promoting knowledge exchange, fostering innovation and advancing scientific research across various disciplines (Hussain et al., 2017; Onyia, 2013). As such, understanding the significance of IT and telecommunications is essential for navigating the complexities of the 21st century and unlocking the potential for societal progress. The academic library stands as a major beneficiary of this discovery.

Academic libraries have long played a pivotal role in supporting the research endeavors of universities and scholarly communities. Traditionally, their primary functions centered around curating print collections, providing reference services and serving as a physical space for study and knowledge exploration (Olubiyo, 2022; Devan, 2020). However, the advent of digital technologies and the rapid dissemination of information have necessitated a transformation in the role of academic libraries. In the digital age, academic libraries have evolved to become vital hubs for facilitating access to a vast array of electronic resources, including e-books, e-journals and online databases (Baskar, 2017). They have embraced digital initiatives such as institutional repositories and open access publishing to promote the dissemination and preservation of scholarly works. Furthermore, academic libraries have expanded their services to encompass virtual

reference assistance, online information literacy instruction and digital scholarship support (O'Beirne, 2017).

As research practices become increasingly collaborative and interdisciplinary, academic libraries have adapted to foster knowledge sharing and interdisciplinary research collaborations. They provide specialized research support services, such as data management, research data curation, and bibliometric analysis to assist researchers in navigating the complexities of modern research workflows (Abubakar, 2017). Moreover, academic libraries have taken on the role of promoting inclusive and equitable access to information and research resources. By embracing initiatives such as open educational resources (OERs) and advocating for open access policies, they strive to democratize access to knowledge and bridge the digital divide (Arthur et al., 2023; Juma et al., 2014). As such, academic libraries are well-positioned to contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge and the fostering of an inclusive research environment within universities.

The convergence of IT, telecommunications and academic libraries presents a unique opportunity to enhance university research inclusion in the digital age. By leveraging the synergies between these three domains, academic institutions can democratize access to knowledge resources, facilitate global research collaborations and promote the dissemination of scholarly works (Aithal & Maiya, 2023; Rugu, 2015). This paper aims to explore the nexus among IT, telecommunications and academic libraries, and how their integration can foster an inclusive and equitable research environment within universities. It seeks to examine the role of digital technologies and communication networks in enabling remote access to library resources, supporting virtual research collaborations and facilitating open-access initiatives. Furthermore, the study will investigate the evolving functions of academic libraries as partners in the research lifecycle, highlighting their potential to bridge the digital divide and promote inclusive access to scholarly materials.

What Does This Paper Seek to Find Out?

Academic libraries play a crucial role in supporting university research and facilitating access to information resources for researchers and students (Bachynska et al., 2024). However, the rapid advancement of IT and telecommunications presents both opportunities and challenges for academic libraries in fulfilling their mission of research inclusion in the 21st century. A significant opportunity is the development and application of IT and telecommunications approaches in library operations, dissemination and access to information leading to

improved library services regarding the provision, distribution and transmission of information (Ofori & Asongu, 2021). On the other hand, a major drawback is the slow integration of digital resources and technologies by academic libraries in developing countries due to political and sociocultural challenges (Sahabi & Otobo, 2021). This paper examines the contemporary direction for academic libraries in leveraging IT and telecommunications to enhance university research inclusion. Specifically, the paper aims to address the following key questions:

1. How has the evolution of IT and telecommunications impacted the role and functions of academic libraries?
2. What are the challenges faced by academic libraries in adapting to the digital age and incorporating technology into their services?
3. How can IT and telecommunications be effectively utilized to enhance university research inclusion?
4. What are the potential benefits and limitations of integrating IT and telecommunications in academic libraries?
5. What are the best practices, case studies and lessons learned from successful implementations of technology in academic libraries?
6. What are the future trends and opportunities for academic libraries in leveraging IT and telecommunications for research inclusion?

By addressing these questions, this paper seeks to shed light on the current state of academic libraries in the context of IT and telecommunications and provide insights and recommendations for libraries to effectively embrace technology to the advantage of users who are either digital natives or digital immigrants and enhance their support for university research inclusion in the 21st century.

Historical Overview of IT and Telecommunications Development

The origins of IT and telecommunications can be traced back to the late 19th and early 20th centuries when groundbreaking inventions paved the way for the digital revolution. The telegraph, patented by Samuel Morse in 1837 was one of the earliest forms of telecommunication, enabling long-distance communication through the transmission of electrical signals over wires (CIT, 2024; Ghimire, 2020). The development of the telephone by Alexander Graham Bell in 1876 marked a significant milestone in telecommunications, allowing for the

transmission of voice over electrical wires (Mushiba, 2024). This invention laid the foundation for modern telephony and the eventual convergence of voice and data communications.

In the realm of computing, the analytical engine designed by Charles Babbage in the 1830s is considered a precursor to modern computers, although it was never fully constructed during his lifetime (Green, 2005). It was not until the mid-20th century that the first electronic general-purpose computers, such as the ENIAC (Electronic Numerical Integrator and Computer) and the UNIVAC I (Universal Automatic Computer) were developed (Brown, 2023; Sen & Agarwal, 2020). The advent of semiconductor technology and the invention of the integrated circuit by Jack Kilby and Robert Noyce in the late 1950s paved the way for the miniaturization of electronic components, leading to the development of smaller, more powerful and more efficient computers (Dixon, 2015). This technological breakthrough laid the foundation for the personal computer revolution of the 1970s and 1980s, with the introduction of iconic machines like the Apple II and the IBM PC (Sen & Agarwal, 2020).

Concurrent with the advancements in computing, telecommunications continued to evolve with the development of satellite communications in the 1960s, enabling global communication and broadcasting. The launch of the first commercial communications satellite, Telstar 1, in 1962, marked the beginning of the satellite communication era. The 1970s and 1980s witnessed the birth of the Internet, which originated from the ARPANET (Advanced Research Projects Agency Network), a project funded by the U.S. Department of Defense (Niehenke, 2014). This decentralized network of interconnected computers laid the groundwork for the modern Internet, facilitating the exchange of data and information on an unprecedented scale.

The 1990s saw the widespread adoption of the World Wide Web, which revolutionized the way information was shared and accessed over the Internet (Liu & Yuan, 2015). This period also witnessed the commercialization of the Internet and the rise of e-commerce, marking a significant shift in the way businesses operate. The 21st century has been characterized by the rapid proliferation of mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, enabled by the development of high-speed wireless networks and the widespread adoption of cloud computing (Gill et al., 2024; Božanić & Sinha, 2021; Pahlavan & Krishnamurthy, 2021). These advancements have further transformed the way we communicate, access information, and conduct business, blurring the boundaries between personal and professional

spheres. Throughout this historical journey, IT and telecommunications have evolved hand-in-hand with every advancement paving the way for new possibilities and innovations. From the early days of telegraphs and telephones to the modern era of the Internet, mobile devices and cloud computing, these technologies have revolutionized nearly every aspect of human existence, shaping the way we live, work and interact with the world around us, including the library.

The digital age has witnessed rapid and transformative advancements in various technologies that have reshaped the way we live, work, and communicate (Collins & Halverson, 2018). At the forefront of these advancements are the Internet, mobile devices and cloud computing. The Internet, a global network of interconnected computer networks, has revolutionized the way we access, share, and consume information. Its widespread adoption and continuous evolution have given rise to numerous applications and services, such as e-commerce, social media, and online collaboration platforms. Mobile devices, including smartphones and tablets, have become ubiquitous, enabling users to stay connected and access information from virtually anywhere (Teoh et al., 2021). The convergence of mobile computing and high-speed wireless networks has facilitated the development of mobile applications, fostering new business models and transforming industries (Galiullina & Wright, 2021).

Cloud computing, which involves the delivery of computing resources (for instance, storage, processing power and software) over the Internet, has emerged as a game-changer in the digital landscape (Surianarayanan & Chelliah, 2019). By offloading computing tasks to remote servers, cloud computing offers scalability, cost-efficiency, and enhanced accessibility to computing resources (Alanezi, 2018). These digital technologies have not only transformed personal and professional spheres but have also had a profound impact on various sectors, including education, healthcare, finance and entertainment. They have enabled new forms of collaboration, data analysis and service delivery, driving innovation and reshaping all industries. As these technologies continue to evolve and converge, their impact on society is expected to become even more significant, paving the way for new opportunities and challenges in the digital era. The advancements in digital technologies, particularly the Internet, mobile devices, and cloud computing, have profoundly impacted various aspects of data management, information access and communication channels (Ramsden et al., 2021; Botta et al., 2016).

Data management has undergone a significant

transformation, with the increasing volume, variety, and velocity of data generated by digital technologies posing new challenges and opportunities. The advent of big data analytics and the ability to process and extract insights from large datasets have enabled organizations to make data-driven decisions and drive innovation (Kumar, 2023). However, this has also necessitated the development of effective data management strategies, including data storage, security and governance practices. Information access has been democratized by the widespread availability of digital resources and the Internet (Balkin, 2017). Individuals and organizations can now access a vast array of information from anywhere in the world, breaking down geographical barriers and fostering knowledge sharing (Moloi et al., 2024). Academic libraries have played a pivotal role in facilitating access to digital resources, such as e-books, e-journals and online databases, enabling researchers and students to access scholarly materials remotely (Olubiyo, 2022).

Communication channels have evolved significantly, moving beyond traditional means such as telephone and postal services. The Internet and mobile devices have enabled real-time communication and collaboration through various channels, including email, instant messaging, video conferencing, and social media platforms (Martin et al., 2022). These digital communication channels have facilitated global connectivity, enabling individuals and organizations to communicate and collaborate across borders and time zones. Furthermore, the convergence of IT and telecommunications has given rise to unified communications systems, which integrate various communication channels into a single platform, enhancing productivity and streamlining communication processes (Wang et al., 2019). Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) technology has also emerged, allowing voice communication to be transmitted over the Internet, reducing costs and enabling seamless integration with other communication channels (Chakraborty et al., 2019). However, the proliferation of digital technologies and the ease of information access have also raised concerns about cybersecurity, privacy and data protection (Sule et al., 2021). As more sensitive information is shared and stored digitally, robust security measures and data governance practices are crucial to mitigate risks and ensure the responsible use of these technologies. Overall, the impact of digital technologies on data management, information access, and communication channels has been transformative, reshaping the way we handle data, access knowledge and communicate with one another, while also presenting new challenges and opportunities that require careful consideration and management.

Academic Libraries in The Digital Era

Academic libraries have long been regarded as the heart of scholarly pursuits within educational institutions, serving as repositories of knowledge and facilitating intellectual exploration. Traditionally, their primary functions have centered on curating and preserving physical collections of books, journals, and other print materials (Maiwada, 2019). One of the core services offered by academic libraries has been providing access to these extensive collections, enabling researchers, students, and faculty members to retrieve relevant materials for their academic endeavors. This involved maintaining comprehensive catalogs and indexing systems, as well as ensuring the proper organization and shelving of resources for easy retrieval (Adeniran, 2017).

In addition to collection management, academic libraries have served as a physical space for study, research and intellectual discourse. They have provided designated areas for quiet individual study, collaborative group work and specialized research facilities such as archives and special collections. Reference services have been an integral part of academic libraries, offering guidance and assistance to users in locating and utilizing information resources (Bandyopadhyay & Boyd-Byrnes, 2016). Librarians have played a crucial role in this regard, providing specialized subject expertise and research consultation to support the information needs of students, faculty and researchers.

Furthermore, academic libraries have traditionally been involved in information literacy initiatives, equipping users with the necessary skills to effectively locate, evaluate and utilize information resources (Rafi et al., 2019). These efforts have aimed to foster critical thinking, research skills and lifelong learning among the academic community. Beyond these core functions, academic libraries have also served as cultural hubs, hosting exhibitions, lectures and other educational events that promote intellectual curiosity and foster a sense of community within the academic setting (O'Donnell & Anderson, 2022). While the traditional roles of academic libraries have centered on physical collections and spaces, the advent of digital technologies has necessitated a significant transformation in their functions and services as they adapt to the changing needs of the academic community in the digital age.

Challenges Posed by Digital Transformation on Academic Libraries

The digital revolution has brought about unprecedented changes in the way information is created, disseminated and accessed, posing significant challenges for academic

libraries as they strive to adapt and remain relevant in the digital age. One of the primary challenges faced by academic libraries is the management and curation of digital resources (Masinde et al., 2021). The proliferation of electronic resources, such as e-books, e-journals, and online databases, has necessitated the development of robust systems for acquisition, organization and preservation (Ibrahim & Tukur, 2023). Ensuring seamless access to these resources while navigating complex licensing agreements and copyright issues has become increasingly complex.

Another challenge lies in the shift towards digital scholarship and the growing demand for specialized research support services (O'Beirne, 2017). Academic libraries are expected to assist with data management, research data curation and bibliometric analysis requiring new skillsets and expertise among library professionals. The rise of open access publishing and the push for democratizing access to scholarly materials have also presented challenges for academic libraries (Knöchelmann, 2021). While promoting open access aligns with their mission of facilitating knowledge sharing, navigating the complexities of open access policies, funding models, and institutional repositories requires significant resources and expertise. Additionally, the digital transformation has necessitated changes in the physical spaces and services provided by academic libraries (Moonasar & Ngoepe, 2023). As more resources become available digitally, there is a need to repurpose physical spaces to accommodate evolving user needs, such as collaborative workspaces, multimedia production facilities, and technology-rich learning environments.

Ensuring adequate funding and resource allocation for these digital initiatives remains a persistent challenge, particularly in the face of budgetary constraints and competing priorities within academic institutions. Furthermore, the rapid pace of technological change and the emergence of new digital tools and platforms demand continuous professional development and training for library staff to keep up with the evolving digital landscape. Amidst these challenges, academic libraries must strike a balance between embracing digital transformation and preserving their traditional roles, while adapting their services and resources to meet the changing needs of the academic community in the digital era.

Opportunities For Innovation and Adaptation For Academic Libraries in The Digital Era

The digital transformation has posed significant challenges for academic libraries and it has also opened up a myriad of

opportunities for innovation and adaptation, allowing them to redefine their roles and services to better meet the evolving needs of the academic community. One of the most promising opportunities lies in the realm of digital scholarship and research support services. By leveraging their expertise in information management and scholarly communication, academic libraries can position themselves as valuable partners in the research lifecycle (Cox, 2021). This includes offering services such as research data management, data curation, bibliometric analysis, and digital publishing support, enabling researchers to navigate the complexities of modern research workflows.

Another area of opportunity is the integration of emerging technologies into library services and spaces. Academic libraries can explore the potential of virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence and other cutting-edge technologies to enhance user experiences, provide immersive learning environments, and facilitate innovative forms of knowledge discovery and dissemination. The proliferation of digital resources and the shift towards open access have created opportunities for academic libraries to champion initiatives that promote inclusive and equitable access to information. By advocating for open educational resources (OERs), institutional repositories, and open-access publishing models, academic libraries can play a pivotal role in democratizing access to knowledge and reducing financial barriers for students and researchers.

Furthermore, the digital era has opened up new avenues for collaboration and resource sharing among academic libraries. Through consortia and collaborative initiatives, libraries can leverage shared resources, expertise, and technological infrastructures, enabling them to provide more comprehensive services and support to their user communities. Adapting physical spaces to accommodate evolving user needs is another opportunity for academic libraries. By repurposing spaces for collaborative work, multimedia production, and technology-enabled learning, libraries can foster a dynamic and engaging environment that supports diverse learning styles and research practices.

To seize these opportunities, academic libraries must embrace a culture of continuous learning, innovation, and adaptation. This may involve developing new skills and competencies among library professionals, fostering partnerships with campus stakeholders, and engaging in ongoing assessment and evaluation of user needs and service models. By capitalizing on the opportunities presented by the digital era, academic libraries can reaffirm their relevance and reinvent themselves as dynamic hubs of knowledge creation, dissemination and preservation, supporting the academic community in the 21st century.

Integration of IT and Telecommunications in Academic Library Services

The convergence of IT and telecommunications has revolutionized the way academic libraries deliver services and resources to their user communities. By leveraging these technologies, libraries have been able to enhance access, facilitate collaboration and provide innovative services that support the evolving needs of researchers, students and faculty members. One of the most significant integrations of IT and telecommunications in academic libraries is the provision of digital collections and resources. Libraries have embraced the transition from physical to electronic formats, offering vast repositories of e-books, e-journals, online databases and other digital materials (Akinola, 2022; Rahman & Khare, 2020). This integration has enabled remote access to library resources, allowing users to access information from anywhere with an internet connection, transcending geographical barriers. Academic libraries have integrated various online research tools and databases to support scholarly endeavors. These include citation management software, bibliographic databases and subject-specific research portals that facilitate literature searches, reference management and data analysis. By leveraging IT and telecommunications, libraries can provide seamless access to these resources, enabling researchers to streamline their workflows and enhance productivity. The integration of IT and telecommunications has enabled academic libraries to offer virtual reference and information literacy services, expanding their reach beyond physical boundaries. Through online chat systems, video conferencing and web-based tutorials, libraries can provide real-time assistance and instructional support to users remotely. This has become particularly valuable for distance learners and researchers working off-campus, ensuring equitable access to library services and resources.

IT and telecommunications have also facilitated collaboration and knowledge sharing among researchers and scholars. Academic libraries have implemented collaborative platforms, such as institutional repositories and research data management systems that enable the dissemination and preservation of scholarly works and research data. Additionally, libraries can leverage videoconferencing and online collaboration tools to support remote research teams, enabling seamless communication and knowledge exchange across geographical boundaries. As academic libraries continue to embrace the integration of IT and telecommunications, they are well-positioned to support the evolving needs of the research community, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations, promoting open access and democratizing access to knowledge resources on a global scale.

Strategies for Enhancing Research Inclusion in Academic Libraries

In the contemporary landscape of academic libraries, the integration of IT and telecommunications has become imperative for fostering research inclusion. To ensure that academic libraries effectively support university research in the 21st century, several strategies can be implemented:

1. Investment in technological infrastructure: Academic libraries need to prioritize investments in robust technological infrastructure that supports seamless access to digital resources, collaboration tools and telecommunications networks (Martzoukou, 2021). This includes upgrading network bandwidth, enhancing Wi-Fi connectivity and adopting cloud-based platforms for data storage and sharing.

2. Digital resource accessibility: Academic libraries should prioritize the digitization of research materials and scholarly resources to ensure universal access for researchers (Nneji, 2018). This involves creating digital repositories, digitizing rare collections and providing online access to journals, databases and e-books. Additionally, libraries should ensure that digital resources are accessible to users with disabilities, thereby promoting inclusivity.

3. Collaborative research spaces: Academic libraries should create collaborative research spaces equipped with advanced IT and telecommunications facilities to facilitate interdisciplinary research collaboration (Cox, 2021). These spaces can include multimedia labs, virtual reality (VR) facilities, video conferencing rooms and data visualization tools. By fostering an environment conducive to collaboration, academic libraries can facilitate cross-disciplinary research initiatives and knowledge exchange among researchers.

4. Integration of emerging technologies: Academic libraries should proactively integrate emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and block chain into their services to enhance research inclusion (Opele, 2023; Okunlaya et al, 2022). For instance, AI-powered discovery tools can help researchers efficiently navigate vast amounts of scholarly literature, while block chain technology can be leveraged to ensure the authenticity and integrity of research data and publications.

5. Promotion of open access initiatives: Academic libraries should advocate for open access initiatives and support the dissemination of scholarly research outputs without access barriers (Siyao et al., 2017). This involves partnering with

faculty members to promote open access publishing models, establishing institutional repositories for preprints and postprints and negotiating transformative agreements with publishers to make scholarly content freely accessible to researchers worldwide.

6. Digital literacy and research skills training: Academic libraries should offer comprehensive training programs and workshops to enhance researchers' digital literacy skills and research capabilities (Yevelson-Shorsher, 2018). These programs can cover topics such as information literacy, data management, research ethics, copyright compliance and citation management. By empowering researchers with the necessary skills and competencies, academic libraries can promote a culture of lifelong learning and scholarly inquiry.

7. User-centered design and feedback mechanisms: Academic libraries should adopt a user-centered approach to design services and resources that meet the evolving needs and preferences of researchers (Bergstrom-Lynch, 2019; Okocha & Eyiolorunshe, 2017). This involves soliciting feedback from library users through surveys, focus groups and user experience assessments to identify areas for improvement and innovation. By actively engaging with stakeholders, academic libraries can tailor their offerings to better support research inclusion and academic success.

Examples of Successful Implementation of IT and Telecommunications in Academic Libraries in Nigeria

Nigerian academic libraries have recognized the importance of integrating IT and telecommunications into their services to enhance access to resources, improve service delivery and support the research endeavors of their user communities. Several institutions have made significant strides in this regard, implementing innovative solutions and leveraging digital technologies to meet the evolving needs of students, researchers and faculty members.

The Kenneth Dike Library at the University of Ibadan has been at the forefront of digital transformation in Nigerian academic libraries. The library has implemented a comprehensive digital library management system, providing access to a vast collection of electronic resources, including e-books, e-journals and online databases (Ojo & Otulugbu, 2016). Users can remotely access these resources through the library's online portal, facilitating research and learning from anywhere with an internet connection. Additionally, the library has embraced virtual reference services, enabling users to seek assistance from librarians through online chat, email and video

conferencing. This has proven particularly valuable for distance learners and researchers working off-campus, ensuring equitable access to library support.

Similarly, the Covenant University Library has made significant strides in integrating IT and telecommunications into its services. The library has developed a robust institutional repository, known as CUlibrary, which serves as a platform for disseminating and preserving the university's research outputs. This initiative has not only increased the visibility and impact of Covenant University's research but has also facilitated knowledge sharing within the academic community. Another university implementing IT for the promotion of research inclusion in Nigeria is Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Ahmadu Bello University's virtual library is a pioneering initiative that leverages IT and telecommunications to provide seamless access to digital resources and online databases. The virtual library offers a user-friendly interface, advanced search capabilities, and personalized features to enhance the research experience for students, faculty and staff. Additionally, the library provides virtual reference services, online tutorials and research guides to support users in navigating digital resources effectively.

Emerging Trends and Technologies in IT And Telecommunications

The landscape of IT and telecommunications is continually evolving, presenting academic libraries with both opportunities and challenges. Emerging trends and technologies include artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, the Internet of Things (IoT), block chain and augmented reality (AR). These technologies have the potential to revolutionize the way academic libraries manage, disseminate and preserve scholarly information. Additionally, advancements in cloud computing, big data analytics and digital preservation techniques are reshaping the way academic libraries store, access and share research data and scholarly resources.

The adoption of emerging technologies in IT and telecommunications has the potential to significantly impact academic libraries and university research. These technologies can enhance research discovery, facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, and improve access to scholarly resources. However, they also pose challenges related to data security, privacy and digital preservation. Academic libraries must navigate these complexities while striving to maintain high standards of service delivery, accessibility and inclusivity for researchers.

Strategies For Academic Libraries to Adapt and Remain

Relevant

In the era of rapid technological advancement, academic libraries face the imperative to adapt and remain relevant in the evolving landscape of IT. To navigate this dynamic environment effectively, libraries must embrace innovation, prioritize user needs and foster collaboration across disciplines and institutions. One key strategy is to foster a culture of innovation within the library ecosystem. By encouraging staff to explore new ideas, experiment with emerging technologies and pursue creative solutions to challenges. Libraries can drive forward-thinking initiatives that enhance research support services and promote academic success.

Moreover, academic libraries should prioritize user-centered design principles to ensure that services, resources and spaces align with the diverse needs and preferences of library users. Understanding the evolving expectations of students, faculty, researchers and other stakeholders is essential for tailoring library offerings to meet their changing requirements effectively. This user-centric approach can inform the design of engaging and intuitive user experiences, fostering greater engagement and satisfaction among library patrons.

Furthermore, academic libraries should play an active role in promoting digital literacy and research skills among users. By offering workshops, training sessions and online tutorials on topics such as information literacy, data management and digital citizenship, libraries can empower users to navigate complex information landscapes, critically evaluate sources and utilize technology effectively in their academic pursuits. Collaboration and partnerships are also crucial strategies for academic libraries to remain relevant in the IT era. By forging alliances with other campus units, academic departments, research centers, and external stakeholders, libraries can leverage expertise, share resources and maximize the impact of their programs and services. Collaborative initiatives such as joint research projects, interdisciplinary seminars and shared collections can enhance the visibility and impact of academic libraries within the university community and beyond. Ultimately, by embracing innovation, prioritizing user needs, fostering collaboration and promoting digital literacy, academic libraries can adapt and thrive in the IT era. By continuously evolving and responding to the changing needs of their users and communities, libraries can fulfil their mission as essential partners in the research, teaching and learning enterprise.

Conclusion

The nexus between IT and telecommunications represents a pivotal paradigm shift in the contemporary direction of academic libraries towards fostering research inclusion in university settings in the 21st century. This research has explored the evolving role of academic libraries as dynamic hubs of knowledge creation, dissemination and discovery, driven by advancements in IT and telecommunications. It has become evident that academic libraries play a central role in supporting university research endeavors by integrating IT and telecommunications into their services and resources. From digital repositories and collaborative research spaces to open access initiatives and digital literacy programs, academic libraries have embraced innovative strategies to enhance research inclusion and promote academic collaboration across disciplinary boundaries.

Moreover, this paper has highlighted the importance of continuous investment in technological infrastructure, staff training and strategic partnerships to adapt to emerging trends and technologies in IT and telecommunications. By prioritizing user-centered design, promoting digital literacy and advocating for open access initiatives, academic libraries can empower researchers with the necessary skills and resources to thrive in the digital age. As we look to the future, the implications of this paper extend beyond the confines of academic libraries to policymakers, researchers and library professionals alike. Policymakers must recognize the critical role of academic libraries in advancing research inclusion and allocate resources accordingly to support technological innovation, open access initiatives and research collaboration. Researchers must actively engage with academic libraries to leverage digital resources, collaborate on interdisciplinary projects, and contribute to the advancement of knowledge. By embracing a culture of collaboration, innovation and ethical conduct, researchers can harness the transformative potential of IT and telecommunications to address pressing societal challenges and drive positive change.

Library professionals must remain vigilant, adaptable and forward-thinking in their approach to service delivery, resource management and strategic planning. By embracing emerging trends and technologies, fostering a culture of lifelong learning and advocating for the needs of their users, library professionals can ensure that academic libraries remain relevant, resilient, and responsive to the evolving needs of the university community.

The following recommendations are made based on the revelations from this paper:

1. Policymakers should prioritize investments in technological infrastructure, digital initiatives and research support services to enhance research inclusion, promote open access and foster academic collaboration.
2. Policymakers should develop policies and regulations that support the adoption of open access publishing models, encourage data sharing and promote the ethical use of digital resources in academic research.
3. Researchers should actively engage with academic libraries to leverage digital resources, collaborate on interdisciplinary research projects and contribute to the development of innovative solutions to pressing societal challenges.
4. Researchers should also advocate for open-access initiatives, support the dissemination of scholarly research outputs and adhere to ethical standards of research conduct.
5. Library and information professionals should embrace innovation, adapt to emerging technologies and anticipate future trends in IT and telecommunications to enhance research services and support academic endeavors.
6. Library and information professionals should also prioritize user-centered design, promote digital literacy and foster a culture of collaboration and innovation within academic libraries.

Hakem Değerlendirmesi: Dış bağımsız.

Yazar Katkıları: Yazarlar ortak katkı sunmuştur.

Çıkar Çatışması: Yazarlar, çıkar çatışması olmadığını beyan etmiştir.

Finansal Destek: Yazarlar, bu çalışma için finansal destek almadığını beyan etmiştir.

Peer-review: Externally peer-reviewed.

Author Contributions: The authors made joint contributions to the creation of the study.

Conflict of Interest: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Financial Disclosure: The authors declared that this study has received no financial support.

References

- Abubakar, B. M. (2021). Library and information science (LIS) education in Nigeria: Emerging trends, challenges and expectations in the digital age. *Journal of Balkan Libraries Union*, 8(1), 57-67.
- Adeniran, A. (2017). *Introduction to library services*. <https://staff.run.edu.ng/oermedia/5233015675129.pdf>
- Aithal, P. S., & Maiya, A. K. (2023). Innovations in higher education industry—shaping the future. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 7(4), 283-311.
- Akinola, S. A. (2022). Management of academic library services in the 21st century digital dispensation. *Alexandria*, 32(2-3), 90-104.
- Alanezi, M. A. (2018). Factors influencing cloud computing adoption in Saudi Arabia's private and public organizations: a qualitative evaluation. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 9(4), 121-129.
- Arthur, P. L., Hearn, L., Ryan, J. C., Menon, N., & Khumalo, L. (2023). Making open scholarship more equitable and inclusive. *Publications*, 11(3), 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications11030041>
- Bachynska, N., Horban, Y., Novalska, T., Kasian, V., & Gaisynuik, N. (2024). University library information resources as a basis for enhancing educational and professional programmes in information, library and archival studies. *Acta Informatica Pragensia*, 13(1), 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.18267/j.aip.229>
- Balkin, J. M. (2017). Digital speech and democratic culture: A theory of freedom of expression for the information society. In *Law and Society approaches to cyberspace* (pp. 325-382). Routledge.
- Bandyopadhyay, A., & Boyd-Byrnes, M. K. (2016). Is the need for mediated reference service in academic libraries fading away in the digital environment? *Reference Services Review*, 44(4), 596-626.
- Baskar, A. (2017). E-resources and its uses in library. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(08), 3588-3592.
- Bergstrom-Lynch, Y. (2019). LibGuides by design: Using instructional design principles and user-centered studies to develop best practices. *Public Services Quarterly*, 15(3), 205-223.
- Botta, A., De Donato, W., Persico, V., & Pescapé, A. (2016). Integration of cloud computing and internet of things: A survey. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 56, 684-700.
- Božanić, M., & Sinha, S. (2021). *Mobile communication networks: 5G and a vision of 6G*. Springer.
- Brown, B. (2023). *Computing Concepts for Information Technology: How computers really work*. Campers' Press.
- CIT. (2024). *The history of information technology: Past and present IT*. <https://www.complete-it.co.uk/the-history-of-information-technology/>
- Chakraborty, T., Misra, I. S., Prasad, R., Chakraborty, T., Misra, I. S., & Prasad, R. (2019). Overview of VoIP technology. *VoIP Technology: Applications and Challenges*, 1-24.
- Collins, A., & Halverson, R. (2018). *Rethinking education in the age of technology: The digital revolution and schooling in America*. Teachers College Press.
- Cox, J. (2021). Positioning the academic library within the institution: A literature review. *Positioning the Academic Library within the University*, 9-33.
- Demir, K., & Akpınar, E. (2018). The effect of mobile learning applications on students' academic achievement and attitudes toward mobile learning. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 6(2), 48-59.
- Devan, N. N. (2020). *Role of academic libraries in research*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339473798_Role_of_Academic_Libraries_in_Research/citation/download
- Dixon, J. (2015). *A brief history of the computer*. John Dixon.
- Galiullina, L. I., & Wright, E. (2021). The influence of Internet – Communication on everyday speech. Special Number: Professional competencies for international university education, 9(2), e1002. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20511/pyr2021.v9nSPE2.1002>
- Ghimire, N. (2020). *Historical development of ICT*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344155798_Historical_Development_of_ICT
- Gill, S. S., Wu, H., Patros, P., Ottaviani, C., Arora, P., Pujol, V. C., ... & Buyya, R. (2024). Modern computing: Vision and challenges. *Telematics and Informatics Reports*, 100116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teler.2024.100116>

- Green, C. D. (2005). Was babbage's analytical engine intended to be a mechanical model of the mind? *History of Psychology, 8*(1), 35-45.
- Hussain, I., Suleman, Q., & Shafique, F. (2017). Effects of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on students' academic achievement and retention in chemistry at secondary level. *Journal of Education and Educational Development, 4*(1), 73-93.
- Ibrahim, N., & Tukur, B. (2023). Selection, acquisition and preservation of e-resources in academic libraries: A reflection of on information resources development and management. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews, 10*(4), 853-862.
- Juma, I. W., Wekullo, C., & Wamukoya, J. (2014). The role of digital libraries in bridging the knowledge gap in Africa. *Mousaion: South African Journal of Information Studies, 32*(1), 64-83.
- Knöchelmann, M. (2021). The democratisation myth: Open Access and the solidification of epistemic injustices. *Science & Technology Studies, 34*(2), 65-89.
- Kumar, N. (2023). Harnessing the power of big data: Challenges and opportunities in analytics. *Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology, 44*(2), 363-371.
- Lawal-Solarin, E. O. (2013). *The use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in academic libraries in Nigeria: A Case Study of Covenant University Library Ota, Nigeria*.
<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/18294899.pdf>
- Liu, S. M., & Yuan, Q. (2015). The evolution of information and communication technology in public administration. *Public Administration and Development, 35*(2), 140-151.
- Maiwada, U. (2019). Online education development and delivery: The role and functions of academic libraries. *SSRG International Journal of Economics and Management Studies (SSRG-IJEMS), 6*(6), 37-40.
- Martin, L., Hauret, L., & Fuhrer, C. (2022). Digitally transformed home office impacts on job satisfaction, job stress and job productivity. COVID-19 findings. *Plos One, 17*(3), e0265131.
- Martzoukou, K. (2021). Academic libraries in COVID-19: A renewed mission for digital literacy. *Library Management, 42*(4/5), 266-276.
- Masinde, J., Chen, J., Wambiri, D., & Mumo, A. (2021). Research librarians' experiences of research data management activities at an academic library in a developing country. *Data and Information Management, 5*(4), 412-424.
- Moloi, K. C., Lebelo, R. S., Dzvimbo, K. P., & Etbaigha, I. (2024). Knowledge management and learning organisation interrelationship towards organisational productivity: University of Technology, South Africa. *Gorteria, 64*(3), 2-20.
- Moonasar, A., & Ngoepe, M. (2023). Disruptive changes in the role of academic libraries and librarians: a case study of a university of technology in South Africa. *Innovation: Journal of Appropriate Librarianship and Information Work in Southern Africa, 2023*(67), 4-31.
- Mushiba, A. (2024). *The evolution of telecommunications: Connecting the world*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378498637_Title_The_Evolution_of_Telecommunications_Connecting_the_World/citation/download
- Niehenke, E. C. (2014). Wireless communications: Present and future: Introduction to focused issue articles. *IEEE Microwave Magazine, 15*(2), 26-35.
- Nneji, K. O. (2018). Digitization of academic library resources: A case study of Donal E. U. Ekong Library. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, Article 1990.
<http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1990>
- O'Beirne, R. (2017). *Academic libraries, open access and digital scholarship—a Delphi study* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Sheffield]. University of Sheffield Theses and Dissertations Archive.
https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/20326/1/OBeirne_Final_EdD_Thesis9052018.pdf
- O'Donnell, P., & Anderson, L. (2022). The university library: Places for possibility. *New Review of Academic Librarianship, 28*(3), 232-255.
- Ofori, I. K., & Asongu, S. A. (2021). ICT diffusion, foreign direct investment and inclusive growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Telematics and Informatics, 65*, 101718.
- Ojo, R. A., & Otulugbu, O. (2016). Using ICT as a platform for effective information services delivery in information age: Kenneth Dike Library, University of Ibadan experience. *Information and Knowledge Management, 6*(6), 44-52.
- Okocha, F., & Eyiolorunshe, T. A. (2017). User centered libraries in Africa: The role of library 2.0 tools. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology, 10*(1), 85-90.

- Okunlaya, R. O., Syed Abdullah, N., & Alias, R. A. (2022). Artificial intelligence (AI) library services innovative conceptual framework for the digital transformation of university education. *Library Hi Tech*, 40(6), 1869-1892.
- Olubiyo, P. O. (2022). Roles of academic libraries in national development. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, Article 6714. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6714>
- Onyia, M. (2013). The impact of ICT on university students' academic studies. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3(8), 105-109.
- Opele, J. K. (2023). The impact of emerging technologies on library education: A global perspectives. *University of Ibadan Journal of Library and Information Science*, 6(2), 191-213.
- Pahlavan, K., & Krishnamurthy, P. (2021). Evolution and impact of Wi-Fi technology and applications: A historical perspective. *International Journal of Wireless Information Networks*, 28, 3-19.
- Rafi, M., JianMing, Z., & Ahmad, K. (2019). Technology integration for students' information and digital literacy education in academic libraries. *Information Discovery and Delivery*, 47(4), 203-217.
- Rahman, R. M., & Khare, V. P. (2020). Electronic resources collection development in university libraries in the digital period: A theoretical study. *Journal of Information Management*, 7(2), 125-137.
- Ramsden, R., Colbran, R., Christopher, E., & Edwards, M. (2021). The role of digital technology in providing education, training, continuing professional development and support to the rural health workforce. *Health Education*, 122(2), 126-149.
- Rugu, V. C. (2015). Adoption of open access initiatives in dissemination of scholarly research by academic staff at selected universities in Kenya [Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi]. University of Nairobi Theses and Dissertations. http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/94709/Rugut_Adoption%20of%20open%20access%20initiatives%20in%20dissemination%20of
- Sahabi, M. K., & Otobo, E. E. (2021). Academic library and challenges of service delivery in Nigerian universities in the digital era. *Information Impact: Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 12(2), 51-61. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ijikm.v12i2.4>
- Sen, S. K., & Agarwal, R. P. (2020). Computing: birth, growth, exaflops computation and beyond. *Decision Making in Social Sciences: Between Traditions and Innovations*, 3-47.
- Singh, A., Shukla, V. K., Seth, A., & Sabitha, S. (Eds.). (2022). *ICT and data sciences*. CRC Press.
- Siyao, P. O., Whong, F. M., Martin-Yeboah, E., & Namamonde, A. (2017). Academic libraries in four Sub-Saharan Africa countries and their role in propagating open science. *IFLA journal*, 43(3), 242-255.
- Sule, M. J., Zennaro, M., & Thomas, G. (2021). Cybersecurity through the lens of digital identity and data protection: Issues and trends. *Technology in Society*, 67, 101734.
- Surianarayanan, C., & Chelliah, P. R. (2019). *Essentials of cloud computing*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Teoh, Y. K., Gill, S. S., & Parlikad, A. K. (2021). IoT and fog-computing-based predictive maintenance model for effective asset management in Industry 4.0 using machine learning. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 10(3), 2087-2094.
- Wang, P., Zhang, J., Zhang, X., Yan, Z., Evans, B. G., & Wang, W. (2019). Convergence of satellite and terrestrial networks: A comprehensive survey. *IEEE access*, 8, 5550-5588.
- Umoren, P. T., & Agwunobi, J. N. (2017). Communication in academic libraries: an assessment of university of Calabar library technique in information services delivery. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 16(1), 47-54.
- Yvelson-Shorsher, A., & Bronstein, J. (2018). Three perspectives on information literacy in academia: Talking to librarians, faculty, and students. *College & Research Libraries*, 79(4), 535.